

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT: AN EFFICIENT SYSTEM TO TRACK ISSUES

ISSUE TRACKING SYSTEM

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Abstract— There have been many applications oriented around controlling and tracing the lifecycle of project, tasks, and requirements. Talking at the grass-root level, students are not yet exposed to the implementation and use of bug tracking system. Through this paper we aim to propose a prototype of an issue tracking system which overcomes many of the limitations of the present day systems and it is also targeted for the use of student groups to aid them in managing various software projects. By providing such a bug tracking system, students are given a chance to experiment with technology that the industry is currently using.

During a system conversion, if staff is well-engaged during the process, all types of issues will be raised, thereafter, there are three challenges faced by the project managers: capturing the issues, acting on the issues, and reporting back to staff about the issues. Of all these, capturing of issues is the most critical and an issue tracking system aids to the same. Issue Tracking System allows individual or group of developers to keep track of outstanding bugs in their product effectively. This can also be called as Bug Tracking System.

Typically bug tracking systems are integrated with other software project management applications. Having a bug tracking system is extremely valuable in software development, and they are used extensively by companies developing software products. Choosing a good bug tracking system for any product will increase productivity of software. This system provided a platform for users from different departments to report issues and understand the latest progress in a product.

Index Terms— *Issues, Bug tracking system, Software development.*

INTRODUCTION

The proposed bug tracking system called Issue Tracking System is an ideal solution to track the bug or issue of a product, solution or an application. Most issue trackers are designed around the central metaphor of the “issue” (bug, defect, ticket, feature, etc.). Issue Tracking System runs with the complete involvement of Project Manager as ADMIN, Developers, and User where Issues or bugs encountered by a user in their application are resolved by the Developers. User and Developer interaction is maintained by Project Manager. Many bug tracking systems, such as those used by most open source software projects, allow users to enter bug reports directly. Other systems are used only internally in a company

or organization doing software development. In Open Source Software development there is a shared understanding among open source developers, reporters and users that efficiently improves the product quality. Yet quality and efficiency of Open Source Software depends upon the bugs present in the product. Thus understanding and tracking of system is vital process. In Open Source Software development tracking of bug is most important step. Bug tracking system contains the large amount of information about the bug in open source software and thus is crucial for tracking the bugs.

Target users for issue tracking register would be clients, software testers, project team members, management members and software developers. It enables multiple users to track and manage multiple projects simultaneously. This system is taking care of the development and support teams as well.

Bug tracking also enables you to know what was done with identified issues, why the system was changed, and what future changes to consider. This application will be written using HTML, CSS, JavaScript, SERVLET, JSP and ORACLE 10g. It is implemented as web application, access through internet using web browser. It supports multiple users and information can be accessed at the same time by multiple users from any type of computer without installing software on user's computer. Since it is a web-based application, users can collaborate from anywhere as long as they have Internet access and a web browser.

Getting acquainted with the pre-requisite of the proposed system:-

- **Issue:** Issue can be described as “non-standard” or “not-awaited” behavior of the system. It can be a bug, but needn't be. This type is usually chosen by people who are not sure how to categorize their problem, and later is usually changed to some other type (bug/enhancement) or closed.
- **Bug:** A software bug (or just “bug”) is an error, flaw, mistake, failure, fault, or “undocumented feature” in a computer program that prevents it from behaving as intended (e.g., producing an incorrect result). Most bugs arise from mistakes and errors made by people in either a program's source code or its design, and a few are caused by compilers producing incorrect code.

OBJECTIVES OF RESEARCH

The objectives of the research are to provide with an issue tracking system which does all of the following:

- Share the information across the team

- Have an instant overview of the state of the software
- Identifying the bugs in the developed application and ensure that No bug will be unfixed in the developed application
- Set and update the importance of individual fixes and adjustments
- Have a recorded history of changes

The system also intends to be an example of an amalgam of development and innovation by proposing a prototype of an Issue Tracking System and at the same time be useful for students to have a glimpse of a software developer who deals with bugs on a daily basis.

IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

Modules and Description

A major component of a bug tracking system is a **Database** that records facts about known bugs. Facts may include the time a bug was reported, its severity, the erroneous program behaviour, and details on how to reproduce the bug; as well as the identity of the person who reported it and any programmers who may be working on fixing it.

Typical bug tracking systems support the concept of the life cycle for a bug which is tracked through status assigned to the bug. A bug tracking system should allow administrators to configure permissions based on status, move the bug to another status, or delete the bug. The system should also allow administrators to configure the bug statuses and to what status a bug in a particular status can be moved. Some systems will e-mail interested parties, such as the submitter and assigned programmers, when new records are added or the status changes.

Fig.1 Issue Management

1. Authenticate User :

Issue Tracking Register first activates the login form. Here User enters the User Name and Password then our system starts the authentication process in which the User Name and Password are matched with the existing username and password in the Database. If the password matches then it is

allowed to the main page (index page) else it warns for Invalid User name and Password. After Successful authentication the system activates menus.

2. Issue Details to track :

In this module User is provided with the facility for adding all the details regarding encountered Issue.

Issue Details includes:-

- [1] Issue Priority.
- [2] Date on which Issue encountered.
- [3] Issue or Bug.

3. Issue Tracking :

After entering all the relevant details related to issue encountered the next step is to track this issue to the project manager. This issue is tracked to the project manager then this issue is assigned to the developer to resolve. Tracking to project manager is done by User and tracking to developer is done by project manager.

4. View :

In this module User can take a look of all the issue's or bug's tracked by his profile. Here User can check whether his issue was resolved or is in progress. This module act as a dashboard of User profile.

5. Developer : This module only belongs to the Developer only. No User Interaction. In this module developer can check which issues is to be resolved. Developer can check the issues details and resolve it as soon as possible and provide feedback of the issue to the Project Manager and the User. Issue resolving can be done on the basis of Issue Priority.

6. Admin (Project Manager) :

Project Manager act as a ADMIN who track all the User Issue's to the different Developers.

Client's

All the Users of this system are displayed in this module. One can add new user or can update the details of an existing user. This module saves the details like client name , contact details , issue's.

Developer's

All the Developers associated with this system are displayed in this module. One can add new Developer or delete existing.

Issue Details and Maintain Issue Chart or Log

Admin can check all the tracked Issues by the Users and then assign these issues to te developers to resolve these. Admin also maintain Issue Log or Chart. In Issue Chart admin maintains details of resolving the issue i.e. Corrective action identified, Stake holders to be consulted, Person responsible, Resources needed, Start and End dates of the resolving process and Current status.

7. Log Out :

In this once the user or admin or developer clicks on log out, First the session is terminated and then the system is redirected to the Login Page.

System Development Environment

I/O REQUIREMENTS

Keyboard	STANDARD
Mouse	STANDARD
Monitor	VGA or XVGA
CD-ROM	4X or above

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

Processor	Intel Dual Core or Higher
RAM	512MB or above
Hard Disk	2 GB or above
Operating System	WINDOWS XP or Higher

SOFTWARE SPECIFICATION

WEB SERVER	Apache Tomcat
7.0.37	
Client Side Language	HTML, CSS, JavaScript
Server Side Language	SERVLET and JSP (JAVA)
Database	ORACLE 10g

SYSTEM DESIGN

The system design had been proposed according to the user requirements and the detail new system. Each issue in the system will have an associated status, priority, and severity. The status indicates the current progress with respect to an issue. Issue

Issue status	Description
Open	It is available for someone to be picked up and solved it
In-Progress	Someone is working on the issue, so no one else should worry about picking it up
Resolved	Someone provided a solution to the issue
Closed	Someone verified the solution and the issue is no more

Fig.2 Issue status type and description

Fig.3 The set of states forms the life cycle of an issue.

When a bug is found, an issue is created in the issue tracking system, and the issue will be in Open state. Once a developer starts working on the issue, the issue will transit to In progress state. When the developer provides a fix for the issue, the issue is then resolved. Priority indicates how soon the issue needs to be attended to. High priority issues are to be attended before the others.

Fig. 4 2nd Level for Project Managers.

Fig.5 2nd level for developers.

CONCLUSION

Innovation is the creation resulting from study and experimentation. It also implies to the art of starting something new for the first time i.e. introducing something new. The paper caters to substantiate the above two definitions of innovation. It not only aims to propose a prototype of Issue Tracking System but also targets to overcome the limitations of the existing system and renders an opportunity to the students to have an exposure of what issues are and can be raised in the software technology and how these issues can be sorted out.

The purpose of the issue tracking register is to test the application for the bugs and report it to the project manager and developer. The main intention behind the Bug Tracking System is that to track bugs and report them. Store the bug information with a unique id in the database for future reference. So, this makes the job of handling the bugs easy. The issue tracking register is an online bug tracking tool initiated with the objective to setup a user-friendly Online bug tracking system. It can be used both for bug tracking and for project management. In this system the project manager can have full details of the work assigned to each team member. Moreover when a new work comes he can assign the work to different persons by having a view at the programmer with minimum work. This software assists to track the work flow of the work given to each team member by a project leader. This software assists the project managers, the team members and equally the top officials of a software company to know how the work is progressing. Project usually comes to the company in the form of bugs. Usually, when certain enhancements of a product is being done i.e. when certain version updates a product is being done, work is assigned to different programmers in the form of Bugs.

Issue tracking system, if used in the right way, can bring following benefits:

- Improve the quality of software.
- Increase satisfaction of users and customers.
- Ensure requests accountability.
- Improve communication in the team and also to customers.
- Increase of productivity of the team.
- Reduce expenses.

The proposed issue tracking register has the following key features:

- **Tasks and Task Manager** – Assign multiple tasks to be completed within an issue. Choose a single task or group of tasks that can be pre-defined or added on the fly. The Task Manager will notify users that tasks have been assigned to them. Tasks can be dependent on other tasks – even cancelled automatically after a specific response to a previous task.
- **Automatic Scheduled Reports** – Reports can be generated and sent automatically to people on an approved distribution list.
- **Tasks with comments and attachments**- One can have comments in every to-do. a small to-do task can be created, and comments and screen shots added in it.

Finally, after reviewing currently available bug tracking systems there were none available that could be used by students as an introduction to using bug tracking systems. Hence, the system is indeed one step forward in the field of innovation and technological development.

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